

Automatic Detection of Corrosion in Ball Bearings of Soft-started Induction Motors using the Persistence Spectrum of the Stray-flux Signals

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Abstract— This work, presents a novel method to automatically detect and classify the presence of corrosion in ball bearings of soft-started induction motors. The method relies, first, in obtaining the persistence spectrum images of the part of the stray-flux signals in which the soft-starter is in operation. Then, those images are used as input for a convolutional neural network, which automatically differentiates not only between healthy or faulty bearings, but also between different levels of corrosion in the ball bearings. For the study, a soft-starter of a well-known brand is used to start an induction motor, setting different combinations of the variable parameters of that device. Also, different levels of load are applied to the motor. The proposed method proves its potential, achieving a high accuracy.

Index Terms— Induction motors, fault diagnosis, stray-flux, convolutional neural networks, persistence spectrum, bearings, corrosion

I. INTRODUCTION

IN many surveys about induction motors (IM) failures, bearing faults represent a high amount of the total reported failures. Depending on the survey, between 40 and 50% of the failures correspond to this type [1], [2]. These kinds of faults have an effect not only on the production, when an unexpected shutdown occurs, but also on the energy consumption of the IM itself, while the failure is evolving. Therefore, it is important to be able to identify these kinds of faults in their initial stages, so maintenance can be properly scheduled, thus reducing losses.

Although vibration data analysis is the most commonly used

This research was funded by the Spanish ‘Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación’, Agencia Estatal de Investigación and FEDER program in the framework of the ‘Proyectos de Generación de Conocimiento 2021’ of the ‘Programa Estatal para Impulsar la Investigación Científico-Técnica y su Transferencia’, belonging to the ‘Plan Estatal de Investigación Científica, Técnica y de Innovación 2021-2023’. (ref: PID2021-122343OB-I00).

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technique in industry for detecting damages in bearings [3], in some industrial applications, this technique cannot be applied due to the impossibility of installing accelerometers on the motor (e.g.: submerged pumps), or because of the high level of noise in the vibration signals (e.g.: traction systems). Thus, the use of other quantities to monitor the condition of the rolling elements of IM becomes necessary. This explains why over recent years, the analysis of electrical quantities to determine the health conditions of electrical motors’ rotating elements has become a trend. In this regard, although some authors report higher difficulties to diagnose bearings when using current analysis, due to the small amplitudes of the fault-related frequencies [4], [5], others report the amplification of some harmonics in the current spectrum when different bearing damages occur [6], [7].

In addition to these methods, stray-flux analysis is other approach to diagnose electrical motors. In this regard, many works have proven the effectiveness of this technique to detect different kinds of faults (e.g.: [8], [9], [10]). Moreover, its non-invasive nature makes this technique even more attractive. Regarding bearing faults, some recent works have also proven the effectiveness of this technique in detecting some of these kinds of damages. These works have applied either statistical analysis (e.g.: [11]), or other techniques such as Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) (e.g.: [12]) to the stray-flux signals. Nevertheless, corrosion damages in bearings have not been very studied, even though it is a typical failure [13]. This fault increments the vibration in the motor, what can lead to faster degradations of its components. It also reduces de efficiency of the motor, increasing its energy consumption. One of the few works studying this fault, is [14]. In it, the authors propose the computation of statistical parameters of the stray-flux signals to detect the presence of corrosion in ball bearings. Although this work shows promising results for the detection of that specific fault, it does not

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differentiate between levels of damage.

On the other hand, the use of different starting methods to limit the stresses that IM suffer during their startups, has become usual in industrial applications. One of the most common starting methods, is the use of soft-starters. These devices, based typically on thyristors, allow to limit the startup current in IM by modifying the RMS value of the supply voltage. But the use of these devices amplifies, and even introduces, some harmonics in the current spectrum and thus, also in the stray-flux spectrum. This fact makes the detection of the typical fault patterns, when the stray-flux signals are analyzed through typical time-frequency tools, more difficult [15].

In this regard, the use of the Persistence Spectrum (PS) in addition to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), has been used in previous works to classify bearing faults (when applied to vibration data) [16] and even rotor faults (when applied to stray-flux signals) [17]. PS is an accumulated bivariate histogram, that shows the power against the frequency, also showing the percentage of time that each power-frequency bin pair is present in the signal. This fact allows to see even slight changes in the evolution of a signal.

Considering all the facts mentioned before, this paper proposes a new methodology to detect and classify between healthy and corroded bearings, in soft-started IMs, as well as to differentiate between different levels of corrosion [18]. The method relies on computing the PS of the part of the combined axial-radial stray-flux signals when the soft-starter is operating (the startup transient plus part of the steady-state). The use of the transient analysis relies on the fact that, as it has been proven in other works (i.e. [19]), many faults amplify their effects during transient regimes, since the currents and stresses are higher, being easier to detect their presence. The resulting PS images are the input of the CNN developed. That CNN allows to classify not only between faulty and healthy conditions, but also between levels of failure, achieving an accuracy rate between 93.8% and 100.00% in all the cases studied. These results give proof of the potential of the proposed method for its eventual incorporation to the soft-starter itself, to turn it into a condition monitoring device.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Detection of Bearing Faults

Typically, when analyzing the current or the stray-flux, the method used to detect bearing faults relies on obtaining the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of those signals. The main idea here, is to identify variations in the amplitude of the fault-related harmonics of each one of the fault types [6]. Those characteristic fault frequencies, are obtained from the expressions used in the vibration analysis [20]. In the vibration spectrum, the characteristic frequency of ball bearings for outer race faults (OR) is given by (1), for inner race faults (IR) is given by (2), for ball faults (BF) is given by (3) and for cage faults (CG) is given by (4):

$$OR = \frac{N_b}{2} \cdot f_r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{BD}{PD} \cdot \cos \theta\right) \quad (1)$$

$$IR = \frac{N_b}{2} \cdot f_r \cdot \left(1 + \frac{BD}{PD} \cdot \cos \theta\right) \quad (2)$$

$$BF = \frac{PD}{BD} \cdot f_r \cdot \left(1 - \left(\frac{BD}{PD} \cdot \cos \theta\right)^2\right) \quad (3)$$

$$CG = \frac{1}{2} \cdot f_r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{BD}{PD} \cdot \cos \theta\right) \quad (4)$$

In the previous equations, N_b is the number of balls of the bearing, BD is the ball diameter, PD is the pitch diameter, f_r is the rotational frequency of the motor and θ is the contact angle.

In the current and/or stray-flux spectrum, the corresponding frequencies are obtained applying (5):

$$f_{bng} = |f_s \pm m \cdot f_{i,o}| \quad (5)$$

In (5), $f_{i,o}$ is the corresponding frequency in the vibration spectrum for each type of failure, f_s is the supply frequency (50Hz) and m is 1, 2, 3, ...

Nevertheless, some previous works have pointed out that assessing those components in the current and/or stray-flux signals, is difficult.

B. Convolutional Neural Networks

The CNNs, which are a type of artificial neural networks (ANN), perform especially well in image recognition due to their characteristics. One of those characteristics, and it is what differentiates them from other ANNs, is that they have in their structure, at least, one convolution layer. The convolution operation extracts the features of the processed images and identifies any existing pattern in them. In [21], the basics of CNNs are exposed.

In this work, the performed CNN has a traditional structure. It has one input layer, five hidden layers (5 x [convolution + batch normalization + ReLu + Maxpool]) and a fully connected layer + a softmax layer + a classification layer at the end. The input for that CNN are the 224x224 PS images obtained. The number of filters for the convolution layers are 16, 32, 32, 64 and 64, being the size in every case 3x3 with a stride of 1x1. In all the pooling layers, the filter size is set in 2x2 and the stride is 2x2. The training algorithm used is the Stochastic Gradient Descent with Momentum (SGDM), because of its simplicity. Finally, the initial learning rate is set in 10^{-3} .

C. Persistence Spectrum

Persistence spectrum (PS) is an accumulated bivariate histogram in the power-frequency space. It is also known as spectrum histogram. It represents the frequency against the power and for every bin of power-frequency pair, shows the percentage of time that it is present in the evolution of the signal. The redder the color is in the PS, the more time that particular power-frequency bin persists in the signal. This is the reason why even the shortest events in the signal, can be seen using the PS [22].

Four are the main steps to obtain the PS, which are the following:

- First, the original signal is split into segments. These segments must have the same length and may or may not overlap. If they overlap, more detailed spectrum analyses will be obtained. The length of the segments, also called time resolution, must have the same or less length than the

signal itself.

- Secondly, for each segment the power spectrum is obtained, thus obtaining the short time Fourier transform (STFT). The STFT matrix is given by (6). The m_{th} element of that matrix, is obtained applying (7) [16], [23], [24]:

$$X(f) = [X_1(f) X_2(f) \cdots X_n(f)] \quad (6)$$

$$X_m(f) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x(n) \cdot g(n - mR) \cdot e^{-j2\pi fn} \quad (7)$$

In those expressions, $X_m(f)$ is the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of windowed data centered in time mR ; $x(n)$ is the input signal at time n , $g(n)$ is the window function (Kaiser window for this work) and R is the number of samples between subsequent DFT.

The power spectrum, for each of the segments, is obtained applying (8) [24], [25]:

$$P_m(f) = |X_m(f)|^2 \quad (8)$$

- In the third step, a bivariate histogram of the power spectrum logarithm is obtained for each time value (segment).
- In the last step, all the bivariate histograms obtained in the third step are used to plot an accumulated histogram. The frequency (Hz) is represented in the X-axis, while the power (dB) is represented in the Y-axis. The color of each power-frequency bin, shows the percentage of time that each component is present in the signal with that amplitude.

The PS, compared to other methodologies, has lower computational requirements. Another advantage is that it is easy to perform. These characteristics, make it an interesting option for its implementation in smart diagnosis systems.

In this work, the overlapping rate between segments is set in 75%. In order to evaluate the influence of the fault both in low frequency and in high frequency, two different frequency ranges were set to obtain the PS. One from 0 to 250Hz and the other from 0 to 1.25kHz.

D. Proposed Methodology

The proposed methodology follows four steps. First, the stray-flux signals are captured, using a handcrafted coil sensor, for 60 seconds. This means that the signal, will contain the startup of the motor and a part of the steady-state. These signals are recorded using a wave recorder. Secondly, as preprocessing, the part of the signal in which the soft-starter is in operation is cut up from the original signal, obtaining the PS image of it. Then, all the PS images obtained are cropped and resized to make them fit for the input restrictions of the CNN. In the last step, the cropped and resized images are used as input for the CNN, following the next randomly chosen distribution: 70% for training, 15% for validation and the last 15% for testing. The images of the test dataset weren't used neither for the training, nor for the validation, so they were new for the CNN. This helped to avoid the risk of overfitting.

Compared to other methods, the proposed methodology has, among others, these advantages:

- Its non-invasive nature, due to the use of an external sensor

to measure the stray-flux.

- The PS images are suitable to apply image recognition systems.
- Lower computational requirements for the obtention of the PS, compared to other methodologies.
- The motor does not need to be uncoupled from its load to apply the method, so it can be considered an online methodology.
- A high accuracy rate is achieved.

III. EXPERIMENTS

In order to prove the methodology, several tests were performed in the laboratory using a 2 pole-pairs, 50Hz, 400V, 1.1kW cage induction motor. This motor was started using 3 models of soft-starters from well-known brands, setting different combinations of the available parameters on those devices (time ramp and initial voltage). On the other hand, the induction motor was coupled to a DC motor, which enabled to apply different levels of load. All these elements can be seen in Fig.1.

For this study, three different health states for the drive end bearing (DE) were analyzed, namely: healthy and two different levels of corrosion. To force the two levels of corrosion, two different brand-new bearings were submerged in a brine solution for 24 hours, for the first level of damage, and for 72 hours for the second one (the brine solution immersion time was considered to be a good reference for determining the corrosion level, and hence the fault severity). After this, the bearing for the first level of damage was let to dry for 3 days before starting the tests. In the case of the second level of failure, the bearing rested for 5 days to dry before starting the tests. Fig. 2 shows images of the three different health states of the bearings. Each one of the models had different topologies, being their main characteristics the ones shown in Table I.

For this study, for the three different health states for the drive end bearing (DE), the tested motor was started 9 times for each combination of time-ramp, initial voltage and load. Four levels of load were applied to the motor: no load, 50%, 75% and nominal load. The different combinations of parameters set in each one of the soft-starters, were those shown in Table II. Therefore, the total amount of images of the dataset was 972, considering all the scenarios. All this variability added complexity to the dataset, a fact that helped to avoid the risk of underfitting in the CNN.

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOFT-STARTERS USED

	Model A	Model B	Model C
Rated power (kW)	1.5	4	1.5
Rated freq. (Hz)	50	50	50
Rated voltage (V)	380-400	400	380-400
Maximum current (A)	3.9	9	3.6
Time-ramp duration (s)	1-20	1-5	0-20
Initial voltage/torque	40%-70%	30%-80%	40%-100%
Controlled phases	R-S	R	R-T

TABLE II
COMBINATION OF PARAMETERS SET IN THE SOFT-STARTERS FOR EVERY TESTED LOAD LEVEL AND FAULT CONDITION

Soft-starter	Combination	Time-ramp (s)	Initial voltage (%)
Model A	1	1	70
	2	10	55
	3	20	40
Model B	1	1	80
	2	3	55
	3	5	30
Model C	1	5	70
	2	10	50
	3	20	40

Fig. 1. Experimental testbench.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. (a) Healthy; (b) First level of corrosion; (c) Second level of corrosion.

Finally, for each startup, the stray-flux was captured placing a coil flux sensor on the frame of the tested motor. This sensor, was handcrafted in the laboratory, having 1,000 turns, an inner diameter of 62mm and being the wire's diameter 0.2mm. After assessing three different models of sensors, this one performed better than the other two. Attending to some works, such as [26], bearing faults can be detected analyzing both the axial and the radial components of the stray-flux. Thus, for economy of both resources and signal

computation, the chosen position for the sensor was such that allowed to capture a combination of the axial and radial stray-flux. The signals were recorded in an oscilloscope and then transferred to a PC, where they were analyzed. The length of the captured signal was 60 seconds, being the sampling rate 10kHz. The PC used for the analyses, training, validation and test processes, had an Intel Core i5-9400 1 CPU (2.9GHz) and 8GB of memory.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since corrosion is a generalized and randomly distributed damage, there is no specific frequency component associated to it. Nevertheless, some of the typically associated frequency components of other bearing faults, such as outer race (OR), inner race (IR), ball (B) or cage (CG) damages, can suffer some kind of variation. The proposed methodology takes advantage of these variations, since PS allows to detect even slight changes in the signals.

For the given characteristics of the bearing, which are those specified in Table III, the frequencies corresponding to the different kinds of failures are those in Table IV. Also, in that table, the frequencies for $f_s \pm m \cdot f_r$ are given for $m = 1$ to 4, since in [14], it is stated that these components show variations due to the presence of corrosion in the bearings.

TABLE III
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BEARING

Parameter	Value
Model	SKF 6205 – 2Z
Number of balls (Nb)	9
Ball diameter (BD)	7.938mm
Pitch diameter (PD)	39.04mm
Contact angle (θ)	0°

TABLE IV
CORRESPONDING BEARING FAULT FREQUENCIES

	$m = 1$		$m = 2$		
	$ f_s - mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s + mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s - mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s + mf_{i,o} $	
OR:	36.04Hz	136.04Hz	OR:	122.08Hz	222.08Hz
IR:	79.96Hz	179.96Hz	IR:	209.92Hz	309.92Hz
BF:	63.15Hz	163.15Hz	BF:	176.31Hz	276.31Hz
CG:	40.44Hz	59.56Hz	CG:	30.88Hz	69.12Hz
	$ f_s - mf_r $	$ f_s + mf_r $	$ f_s - mf_r $	$ f_s + mf_r $	
	26.00Hz	74.00Hz		2.00Hz	98.00Hz

	$m = 3$		$m = 4$		
	$ f_s - mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s + mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s - mf_{i,o} $	$ f_s + mf_{i,o} $	
OR:	208.12Hz	308.12Hz	OR:	294.16Hz	394.16Hz
IR:	339.88Hz	439.88Hz	IR:	469.84Hz	569.84Hz
BF:	289.46Hz	389.46Hz	BF:	402.62Hz	502.62Hz
CG:	21.32Hz	78.68Hz	CG:	11.76Hz	88.24Hz
	$ f_s - mf_r $	$ f_s + mf_r $	$ f_s - mf_r $	$ f_s + mf_r $	
	22.00Hz	122.00Hz		46.00Hz	146.00Hz

The images in Figs. 3 and 4 have been selected so, for each model of soft-starter, the settings of time-ramp, initial voltage and level of load were the same. Between models, the images have been selected so the time-ramp and initial voltage would be as similar as possible (attending to the setting options of each device), and for the same level of load.

Fig.3 shows the PS images for every model of soft-starter and for the three considered health states of the DE bearing, namely healthy, first level of corrosion (corrosion 1) and the second level of corrosion (corrosion 2). In this case, the represented frequencies go from 0 to 250Hz. Note that the differences between the three levels of failure are distributed, mainly, along the frequencies related to CG damages when $m = 1$ to 10 and OR, IR and BF when $m=1$ and 2. Also the frequencies corresponding to the components given by $f_s \pm m \cdot f_r$ (when $m = 1$ to 10) show variations as the failure worsens.

As an example, in Fig. 3 some regions are highlighted. Although

the variations in the PS are not limited to those regions, centering the scope in them is useful to explain some concepts. Observing those regions for models B and C (Fig. 3(b), (c), (e), (f), (h) and (i)), the components contained in them, move to the upper part of the spectrum as the fault worsens, making the color in that section of the spectrum redder. Stated yet another way, the components contained in those regions, stay longer in the signal, with a higher amplitude, as the fault worsens. This fact is consistent with what was expected in this kind of fault, for all the characteristic frequencies of all the ball bearing failures should show variations when corrosion exists. Moreover, as the corrosion worsens, the amplitudes of those components, in general, increase in the PS.

On the other hand, what has been stated for models B and C is only valid for the model A in region 2 (Fig. 3 (a), (d) and (g)). That region contains mainly the frequencies related to the rotational frequency (f_r). Nevertheless, the PS images have, in every case, differences enough to allow the CNN to differentiate between health states of the bearing.

Fig. 3. PS images, from 0 to 250Hz, when using the soft-starter model A, B and C: (a), (b) and (c) Healthy state; (d), (e) and (f) Corrosion 1; (g), (h) and (i) Corrosion 2; (j), (k) and (l) Confusion matrices for each model.

Fig. 3 (j), (k) and (l) show the confusion matrices resulting from the application of the CNN to the PS images representing from 0 to 250Hz. Note that the achieved accuracy rate goes from 93.8% to 100% depending on the model of soft-starter. Besides, in all the cases the mismatches occur between levels of fault. This means that the proposed methodology can detect not only the presence of the studied fault, since it discriminates perfectly between healthy and faulty states, but also can discriminate between the different levels of fault achieving a high accuracy rate. Just for clarifying purposes, the number of samples in the confusion matrices correspond to the number of images in the test dataset. Since for each model of soft-starter the total amount of images was 108 per health state, the 15% is 16.2. Taking the closest integer, the number of samples per health state is 16.

Widening the scope of the PS analysis, Fig. 4 shows the PS images, for the three considered health cases of the bearing and for frequencies from 0 to 1,250Hz. In general terms, the variations in the PS are mainly located in the components corresponding to all the bearing fault types (in this case, for m from 1 to 10) and in the $f_s \pm m \cdot f_r$ components.

Also here, three regions are highlighted as an example, although the variations are not restricted to those regions. Note that in them, in general terms, for the models A and C the components concentrate in the upper side of the spectrum as the fault worsens. This means that, also in this case, the frequencies corresponding to the typical bearing faults, such as OR, IR, BF and CG (see Table IV), have higher amplitudes along more time as the signal evolves. On the contrary, for the case of the soft-starter model B the trend is different if we focus only in those regions.

Fig. 4 (j), (k) and (l) shows the confusion matrix resulting from the application of the CNN to these images. In this case, the accuracy achieved is 100% for all the cases. This means that the proposed methodology can discriminate not only between the healthy and the faulty state with no error, but also between different levels of corrosion.

Attending to the results, the topology of the device seems to affect the results. The number of controlled phases, what phases are controlled by the device and even the time settings (see Table II) can affect the evolution of the components in the spectrum. Nevertheless, there are differences enough in the PS to allow the CNN to classify the health state of the bearing for every model of soft-starter.

Looking at the images in Fig. 3 (j), (k) and (l) and Fig. 4 (j), (k) and (l), for both models A and B the accuracy rate is lower when using the images of the PS from 0 to 250Hz as input, than when using the PS images from 0 to 1,250Hz (this latter frequency range includes some of fault frequencies (see Table IV) that are not contained in the first range). Nevertheless, the lowest accuracy rate is 93.8%, which is still quite a good result.

Finally, all the PS images obtained for all the models of soft-starters and health states of the bearing were merged in two datasets. The first one, with the PS images from 0 to 250Hz and the second one, with the PS images from 0 to 1,250Hz. Fig. 5 shows the resulting confusion matrices for each case.

For both cases, the final accuracy rate was 98.6%. Moreover, the method can differentiate, with no error, the healthy state from the faulty ones. The misclassifications only occur between levels of fault, but the accuracy rate in these cases is still high (95.9%), what allows to say that the method is able to differentiate between levels of fault too.

Again, just for clarifying purposes, the number of samples in the confusion matrices correspond to the number of images in the test dataset. Since for all the models of soft-starters the total amount of images was 324 per health state, the 15% is 48.6. Taking the closest integer, the number of samples per health state is 49.

Additionally, the Recall, the Precision and the Accuracy values are provided in the confusion matrices. Besides, Table V shows the F1-Score values of the CNN for all the cases studied, proving the good behavior of the method.

Fig. 4. PS images, from 0 to 1,250Hz, when using the soft-starter model A, B and C: (a), (b) and (c) Healthy state; (d), (e) and (f) Corrosion 1; (g), (h) and (i) Corrosion 2; (j), (k) and (l) Confusion matrices for each model.

		Target Class			
		Corrosion ₁	Corrosion ₂	Healthy	
Output Class	Corrosion ₁	49 33.3%	2 1.4%	0 0.0%	96.1% Precision
	Corrosion ₂	0 0.0%	47 32.0%	0 0.0%	100% Precision
	Healthy	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	49 33.3%	100% Precision
		100% Recall	95.9% Recall	100% Recall	98.6% Accuracy
(a)					
		Target Class			
		Corrosion ₁	Corrosion ₂	Healthy	
Output Class	Corrosion ₁	47 32.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	100% Precision
	Corrosion ₂	2 1.4%	49 33.3%	0 0.0%	96.1% Precision
	Healthy	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	49 33.3%	100% Precision
		95.9% Recall	100% Recall	100% Recall	98.6% Accuracy
(b)					

Fig. 5. Confusion matrices when using all the models at a time: (a) for PS from 0 to 250Hz; (b) for PS from 0 to 1,250Hz.

TABLE V
F1-SCORE VALUES FOR EACH OF THE STUDIED CASES

		Model A			Model B			Model C			All Models		
		Frequency band: 0 – 250Hz											
Metrics	Class	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy
	F1-Score	90,3%	90,9%	100,0%	97,0%	96,8%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	98,0%	97,9%	100,0%
		Frequency band: 0 – 1,250Hz											
Metrics	Class	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy	Corr_1	Corr_2	Healthy
	F1-Score	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	97,9%	98,0%	100,0%

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new methodology is proposed to automatically detect the presence of corrosion in ball bearings of soft-started induction motors. Even more, this method allows to differentiate between levels of the studied failure (bearing corrosion). The use of the stray-flux signals in addition to the PS analysis and the application of a CNN, has proven its potential, achieving a high accuracy rate not only in the detection of the failure, but also in differentiating between levels of failure.

Since corrosion is a common failure in bearing balls and traditional approaches, such as FFT or time-frequency tools, do not provide reliable information about it when applied to stray-flux or current, the results obtained in this work are promising and can complement other methods to reliably detect this specific fault.

Apart from focusing on a barely studied fault in the literature (bearing corrosion problems which can simultaneously affect different parts of the bearing), the main contribution of the work is to prove the effectiveness of the persistence spectrum to automatically identify fault harmonics in applications where the signal-to-noise ratio is low, such as soft-started motors. Moreover, the use of stray-flux signals for bearing corrosion detection is proven to be effective according to the results.

Regarding the future works, in order to confirm that these results can be generalized, the authors intend to perform additional tests in other types of motors. Also, different types of faults affecting not only the bearings, but also other components will be analyzed.

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